

Pink Marketing and Women's Purchasing Decision Making

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This study mainly aimed to investigate the impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions. Two main sources of collecting necessary data for this study have been relied on: Secondary data sources which included, internet, periodicals, references, literature review related to the study, to explain the basic concepts, and identifying the most important studies that dealt with the study subject. Primary data sources included designing a questionnaire to gather data from women who deal with Amman cosmetics market. pink marketing mix elements (pink product, pink price, pink promotion, and pink distribution) were adopted as independent variables while women's purchasing decisions were the dependent variable. The study relied on descriptive and analytical methods, the study population included women customers in Amman cosmetics market, and a convenience sample of 100 women customers who deal with Amman cosmetics market has been selected. The main findings of the study were: There is a statistically significant impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions. There is a statistically significant impact of each one of the marketing mix elements (pink product, pink price, pink promotion, and pink distribution) on women's purchasing decisions.</i></p>
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INTRODUCTION

They say women are half of society, with the presence of women in different areas of life, focusing on them in preparing marketing strategies has become necessary because they play an important role in the life of a society, including in making important decisions at different levels, but from marketing point of view, women are not only half of society, but more than that, as marketing studies say that 85% of the purchasing decisions made by women or affected by them (Shehata and Fayyad, 2020, p.221). So interest in the issue of women has become a fundamental issue in human social treatments (Khasawneh, 2015, p.5). Hence, this great influence of women in purchasing decisions called on both marketing experts and practitioners to devise new marketing methods and techniques that suit their nature and fit their needs, desires, way of thinking, and purchasing motives. These marketing tactics geared toward women are called Pink Marketing, which is one of the marketing types that appeared in the twenty-first century, refers to women, and all marketing efforts directed to women. Since the behaviors of women differ fundamentally in many aspects from that of men, understanding the needs of women as a customer, who contributes to the process of purchasing and consuming decision-making, or as a marketer who own skills in the performance of her marketing tasks, becomes more urgent (Gharib, 2015, p.4). Accordingly, organizations around the world have begun to concern on identifying women's needs and desires as a target market segment, working to satisfy them, and studying the marketing factors affecting their purchasing decisions, to achieve their satisfaction and gain their loyalty (Kraft and Weber, 2012, P. 248; Alexandra and Melnyk, 2016, PP.1553).

1. PINK MARKETING CONCEPT

Pink marketing is one of the modern terms in marketing, which organizations strive to apply. This term has led marketing scholars and experts to use it as an indication of women-oriented marketing, as pink is the color of femininity (Gharib, 2015, p.2). Some believe that pink marketing term is limited to women's sales teams that are formed within the institution to take care of female customers, and some define it as: How do you market to women? It is more correct that women's marketing is those marketing efforts implemented by women's knowledge, or targeted to female customers, or marketing from and to women (Abdel Fattah, 2017, p.17). Pink marketing is also defined as a marketing strategy based on targeting women with company's products so that the marketing techniques used by the company are more effective on women than they have on men because women's psychological nature differs from that of men, and this means that the motives for purchasing in women differ from that in men, and thus, women's purchasing behavior differs from that of men (Fares, 2020, p.4). Women's marketing, or what is known in foreign literary writings, as pink marketing does not only focus on aspects of marketing that target women as a customer or buyer, but also aims to address the role of women in serving the areas of marketing in general, whether those serving girls' customers or that use marketing

plans and issues for the market as a whole (Osama,2008,p.15). Pink marketing also defined as the application of marketing mix elements (product, price, promotion and distribution) in a way that is proportionate and Compatible with women's psyche and lifestyle, to meet their needs and desires in an optimal way that enables them to be loyal to product (Qaddumi,2017,p.95). Pink marketing is also defined as all of the marketing activities and efforts targeted to female customers including: product, price, distribution, and promotion in a way that suits women. It is a mistake for the organization to apply pink marketing by following a rosy approach when addressing women with its marketing messages, because this approach is characterized by a stereotype that no longer applies to women. What is required today is marketing messages that show an understanding and conformity with women's psyche and needs (Babiker, 2017, p.7). Pink Marketing is the marketing effort that seeks to fulfill women's needs and desires in terms of goods and services, through gathering marketing information that correspond to their attitudes and tastes (Obaidi, 2017, p.402). It is noticed that pink marketing is not limited to selling products to women, but extends to products directed to men, as women influence men's purchasing decisions. That is, companies should target women in marketing campaigns, as they influence the purchasing decision-maker, and this requires the use of marketing cleverness in marketing campaigns for products directed to men, children, and family, through sending signals or suggestions that affect women and make them convince men or children to buy these products (Abdel Fattah,2017,p.17). pink marketing is also defined as those marketing efforts that target women as customers, or that are implemented with their knowledge as marketers (Saeed& Sabriina, 2015,p.4). Pink marketing or women-oriented marketing is also defined as a marketing strategy based on targeting women through organizations that produce or market products (Saud, et al.,2020, p.344).

Through the previous definitions, we conclude that pink marketing is an activity directed to women or from women, consists of a group of activities called marketing mix elements, which are formulated according to women's requirements, desires, and psyches, to affect their attitudes and behaviors in what they would like to own, and even towards what others would like to own when they influence their purchasing decisions.

2. PINK MARKETING MIX ELEMENTS

When designing the proper pink marketing mix, whether it is for a commodity or a service, it should be taken into account to focus on the emotional temptations in the characteristics of the marketing program, due to the distinctive emotional nature of women (Li, et al.,2015). While Osama (2013) confirms to Pay more attention to the quality and value of the presented product by adapting pink marketing mix elements to personality characteristics dimensions of female's, without using marketing deception to customer.

2.1 Pink product

It is the one which characteristics coincide with women's desires and tastes since it differs from the one directed to the rest of the customers. While men search for the ultimate benefits of products and services provided to, such as the price and the characteristics of tangible product that addresses their reason and logic, women attention is given to some details related to their taste and affection, so women are more interested in intangible characteristics that affect their morale and psychological side (Li et al.,2015). Alexandra and Melnyk, (2016) also emphasized the need to distinguish pink product directed to women, because they always need to purchase the best and the distinctive one, therefore, advantages and benefits of it with the comparison of competitors one, attention to its shape and packaging, must be shown. when they purchase women are always looking for a product that is characterized by: new, keeps pace with the developments of the times, diversity, and developed according to their needs and desires (Kadhim et al.,2016,pp:357-359). An example of product development according to women's desires and interests is the orientation toward friendly green and environmentally products, due to women's concern of their family's health, and food products they purchase for their children, also more weight should be given to its quality, since women are looking for quality, not quantity, in the presented product (Anderson and Howland, 2006; Alexandra and Melnyk, 2016).

3.2 Pink price

Men differ from women in their perception and evaluation of price. The man may see the offered price as high, while the woman may think that it is fair or appropriate because women search for the true value associated with the product, and how it relates to their requirements and needs of their families (moral needs) (Li et al.,2015). When pricing pink products, marketers must take into account the suitability of the price with the quality and the characteristics of other products, because a woman looks at prices in an integrative manner, which is known as the complementary reciprocal relations between the price and the other elements of the marketing mix (Kadhim et al.,2016,pp:357-359). While Obaidi (2017) indicated that women prefer high price (skimming price) as they see that the higher price reflects a higher quality and a higher value of the product, that meet their moral needs, men may not see it as a high price. Li et al (2015) indicated that low prices may push some women to buy products that they do not need at present time, but the low price or special offers are what pushed them towards purchasing, which is known as the term "impulse purchasing".

3.3 Pink promotion

It represents the way to communicate with female customers without exploiting their innate tendencies and weaknesses, in addition, it should be noted that women are more emotional than men, as they are more concerned with emotions than logical information, also, they are convinced of the product more through their emotions, while men are convinced of the product through mental judgment, so organizations that target women with their products should focus on emotional temptations in their advertising and marketing campaigns more than logical information, for example, focusing on feelings in advertising, music, and colors, also, products geared toward mother should focus on emotions of motherhood and mother's tenderness for her children (Obaidi, 2017, p.409). Nowadays, the means of advertising and promoting products have been developed and moving towards trying the product before purchasing it, to reach the most important methods of persuasion and promotion. Based on word of mouth that lists the successful experiences of the product, it was found that 64% of mothers ask their friends about their evaluation of the product they tried, before purchasing it, and this highlights the importance of word of mouth in pink marketing (Obaidi, 2017, p. 410). Women are greatly affected by the communication content, and it is necessary to choose a promotional mix that addresses their desires and emotions while showing the logical aspects of the quality and value of the product. The results of Delia's (2015) study, which discussed the impact of promotional content on women, showed that 91% of the study sample confirmed that targeted ads do not understand the needs of women and how to influence them. Therefore, emphasis must be placed on personal communication through an understanding of the customer's personality and preferences, for example when designing advertisements directed to women, the colors that women prefer should be chosen which are warm colors such as pink and red (Abdel Fattah, 2017). The University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA, study showed that 70% of promotional content remains in women's minds and has been affected by)Kraft and Weber, 2012). Johnson's study (2015) showed that one of the most influential elements of women's promotional mix is social media on the internet, where most women spend their time on social media, as nearly 89% of women have accounts on social networks.

3.4 Pink distribution

It represents the place where the product is sold to female customers, with the need to take into account their tastes in colors and exterior and interior designs. Men focus more on physical elements in the stores, so they are interested in having cars parks to park their cars and focus on store inventory, while women are interested and focus on the design of the store, the decoration of the store, the way they are treated by sales personnel (Obaidi, 2017, p.407). To ensure effective distribution for its products, an organization must use a wide and strong distribution network, to reach consumers effectively and efficiently, and this can be achieved by making its product available and accessible, with the help of stores, supermarkets, and shopping centers (Qaddumi, 2017, p.97). Direct, indirect distribution channels and electronic distribution outlets (websites, or online reservation sites such as Booking.com) represent one of the basic components of the marketing environment that affects customer's purchasing decisions. Women are strongly affected by the quality of the distribution outlets, their external and internal design, and the colors used, unlike men who care about the physical aspects, such as proximity of the distribution outlets and the ease of reservation (Lieven et al., 2015). Therefore, attention must be paid to raising distribution outlets efficiency and quality, and it is preferable to use selective distribution outlets in case of targeting women, this is done through the selection of a qualified mediator, with the need to continuous evaluation of the feasibility of using it, and the level of its employee's qualifications, skills of influence, and persuasion in dealing with women (Kadhim et al., 2016).

3. THE CONCEPT OF WOMEN'S PURCHASING DECISIONS

purchasing process consists of several steps that a woman must go through to make a purchasing decision, most theories that have been interested in studying and preparing procedures for making purchasing decision are based on considering that purchasing is a process to solve a problem so the difficulty of solving a problem varies according to the type of pink commodity or service. woman's decision is: "Choosing an alternative from among many possible alternatives" to reach a goal, solve a problem, and seize an opportunity (Taha, 2008, p.138). In pink marketing, the purchasing decision-making process can be summarized as, steps or stages that a woman goes through, including conducting tests to any goods or services she prefers to buy) Babiker, 2017, p.22). It is also known as: "The process of differentiation between alternatives, that is, the process of choosing the best alternative that better meets the needs of woman"(Abdali and Allaq, 2006, p.52). Through the previous definitions, we conclude that the decision-making process is those steps and stages that a woman undertakes by collecting information and analyzing it to compare the alternatives to choose the best alternative, to achieve the desired goal to solve a particular problem.

4. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PINK MARKETING MIX DIMENTIONS AND WOMEN'S PURCHASING DECISIONS

Pink marketing mix represents a set of activities carried out by product organizations to influence women's behaviors and push them to purchase their products and achieve their satisfaction, they are:

5.1 The effect of pink product on a woman's purchasing decisions

Every institution tries to establish and impose itself in the woman's market by creating a pink product that is distinct and has a competitive advantage from competitor's one. From the consumer's point of view, the product is not only everything that the officials of the organization think about producing, but the most important thing is how to influence customers through their principle of the product's value they aim to achieve, to think about acquiring it (Ben Dahman, 2017, p.83) It becomes clear that woman, as the main consumer in the market, is the one who imposes her desire in a form of a pink product, we can say that pink product marketing goal is the degree of compatibility between the pink product itself and the characteristics of a woman, what she expects from the product and her urgent need that pink product meets and satisfies(Almusaeid,2016, PP.56-57).

5.2 The effect of price on a woman's purchasing decisions

Pink pricing represents how much women customers pay for a product without exploiting their weaknesses, pink price and the decisions related to are the most difficult decisions facing marketing men because they must take into account women on the one hand, and achieve the goals of the organization in integration with the rest of the marketing mix elements in light of the restrictions represented by all the factors affecting the price whether internal or external on the other hand, and marketers must adopt pricing methods and techniques to influence woman's purchasing decision (Azzam, et al.,2008, p.266).

1.3 The effect of promotion on a woman's purchasing decisions

Promotion is one of the elements that most affect women, as it represents the means that allows women to discover pink products that they do not know. It is an essential element of the organization's activities. It plays the role of a link between women's needs and organization's product through several components, include (Ben Dahman, 2017, p.97):

5.3.1 Advertising

The success of the advertisement in influencing women's behavior depends mainly on the content of the advertising message, the means of advertising, and the appropriate time for advertisement, there is a group of women affected by advertising on television since organizations adopt, for example, a famous person who influences their purchasing decisions, and the frequency of advertisement breaks the barrier of hesitation and make them take their pink product purchasing decisions, besides, there are institutions that adopt advertising by using the internet, and social media sites to encourage them making their purchasing decisions for the pink product offered.

5.3.2 Sales promotion

Every woman has her own characteristics that she shares with other women, as well as every organization has its methods that rely on influencing a woman's purchasing decisions, including (Boumala and Makhnach,2019, p.65):

- The front display shows that woman sees in the shops, which lead her to purchase.
- The free samples provided by shops may make a woman purchase unnecessary products.
- The samples she gets encourage her to purchase quickly and in large quantities.
- Price discounts encourage women to acquire products.

5.3.3 Personal selling:

It represents the direct contact between the woman as a customer and the seller. The organization relies on a sales representative to influence the woman's purchasing decision. The organization must choose the representative who has all the qualifications starting from the external appearance to the tactful manner of dealing and can persuade. Personal communication plays three roles, which are Boghda & Khalaf, 2018, p.46):

- Selling: when trying to find new customers or increase sales to existing customers.
- Providing the service: The service can be in the form of advice or customer assistance and others.
- Control: means monitoring the development of the relationship between customers and competitors.

5.3.4 Public Relations

Since public relations management responsibility is as an outlet of marketing activities in the organization, public relations can be defined as a promotional activity aimed at forming a favorable image to women about the marketed product. In general, the most important services provided by the Public Relations Department are as follows:

(Boumala and Makhnach,2019, p.66):

-Developing close relationships with women through contacting them and learning about their needs and problems.

- Preparing and disseminating information about the organization through annual reports, personal interviews, and establishing programs such as charity parties, film screenings, and exhibitions.

5.4 The effect of distribution on a woman's purchasing decisions

Distribution is considered one of the important marketing mix elements of any product, any new, distinct, advertised, and sold at an attractive price product may not mean anything to customers, if it is not available to them in the place and time they request, and thus distribution is the activity that allows the display of products to customers at the right time and place. When the woman wants to meet a specific need, she goes to point of sale or store that is known as the meeting point between the seller and the buyer. The location of the store, the variety of services offered, and the general atmosphere of the store, are the most important points that affect the final customer's purchasing decisions (Al-Nsour, 2013,p.357).

6. PROBLEM OF THE STUDY

It has become very important to conduct marketing studies that address marketing women's issues. The need to conduct marketing studies dealing with women's marketing issues has emerged, as it becomes clear that women are the main consumers in the market, hence the current study seeks to know the impact of pink marketing mix elements, on women's purchasing decisions. Accordingly, this study tries to answer the following main question:

What are the impacts of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions?

From the main question, we can deduce the following sub-questions:

- What is the impact of the pink product on women's purchasing decisions?
- What is the impact of pink prices on women's purchasing decisions?
- What is the impact of pink promotion on women's purchasing decisions?
- What is the impact of pink distribution on women's purchasing decisions?

7. Importance of the study

From a theoretical perspective, this study tries to present pink marketing modern concepts and their impact on women's purchasing decisions in light of lack of information in this area, since understanding pink marketing and how it affects women's purchasing decisions enables marketers who deal with women consumers to reach the desired goal. While from a practical point of view, the study contributes to knowing the real impact of the pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions, specifically in the field of cosmetics, and thus the possibility of achieving greater effectiveness in marketing strategies adopted by companies in the cosmetics market. This enables companies to achieve profits and preserve their market share.

8. Objectives of the Study

The study aims mainly to test the impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions in Amman cosmetics market. It also aims to:

- Know about the reality of pink marketing in Amman cosmetics market.
- Shedding light on the importance of conducting scientific research related to women, especially in the marketing fields.

9. Hypotheses of the study

The field study was designed to investigate the main hypothesis and several sub-hypotheses, as follows:

The main hypothesis:

Ho: There isn't any statistically significant impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions.

The sub- hypothesis:

Ho1: There isn't any statistical significant impact of the pink product on women's purchasing decisions.

Ho2: There isn't any statistically significant impact of pink price on women's purchasing decisions.

Ho3: There isn't any statistically significant impact of pink promotion on women's purchasing decisions.

Ho4: There isn't any statistically significant impact of pink distribution on women's purchasing decisions.

10. Methodology of the study

The study relied on descriptive and analytical methods, where phenomena and events are studied as they are in terms of their characteristics, forms, and factors affecting them. It studies the presence of phenomena and events by describing them with all aspects and dimensions to identify causes and relationships that led to these phenomena and events, as well as determine the relationships with each other and the external factors affecting them to benefit from them in predicting their future and extract solutions. (Dashli,2016, p.61).

10.1 Population and Sample

Due to the large size of the study population, which included different societal segments of women who deal with Amman cosmetics market, a convenience sample of 100 women has been selected, and a total of (80) valid questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed. Hence, the woman can be regarded as the unit of analysis for this study.

10.2 Data collection tools

A questionnaire to collect data for the current study and its variables was designed, it included (28) statement to measure the extent of pink marketing mix elements impact on women's purchasing decisions.

10.3 Sources for obtaining data

Two main sources of collecting necessary data for this study have been relied on: Secondary data sources which included, internet, periodicals, references, literature review related to the study, to explain the basic concepts, and identifying the most important studies that dealt with the study subject. Primary data sources included designing a questionnaire to gather data from women who deal with Amman cosmetics market.

10.4 Statistical analysis methods used:

Since they agree with the nature of data available, and to analyze variables and testing hypotheses of the study both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were the most appropriate used, they are:

- 1- To describe the sample responses concerning pink marketing mix elements, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviations, relative importance, degree of agreement) were used.
- 2- To test the hypotheses of the study (the impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions).
multiple regression analysis was used.
3. Cronbach's Alpha test to measure the internal consistency between questionnaire statements, and then to determine the degree of reliability of the tool.

10.5 Validity and reliability

1. Validity: The questionnaire had been judged by many marketing studies specialists to ascertain its validity (the ability of the instrument to measure the variables that are designed to measure).
2. Reliability: Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to measure the internal consistency between statements of the questionnaire, to determine the degree of reliability of the tool. The test result was (.78) for all statements belong to both independent and dependent variables in the questionnaire, which is higher than the acceptable limit (.60).

11. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Before starting to review the field study, it must be noted that cosmetic products are: substances that include skincare, haircare, dye products, perfumes, as well as mouth care products (Rekha and Gokila,2015).

This section of the study consists of two parts, the first is for statistical analysis of the sample responses concerning Pink marketing mix elements and woman's purchasing decisions. While in the second the main hypothesis, and sub- hypotheses emanated from, have been discussed and analyzed. The statistical analysis has been done in the context of cosmetic sector women customers. The following tables show the results:

11.1 Analysis of the respondents' opinions of pink marketing mix elements and woman's purchasing decisions.

Tables (1,2,3,4,5) below, show us, mean, standard deviation, relative importance, and degree of agreement of the respondents (women) responses in terms of pink marketing mix elements and woman's purchasing decision statements.

Table (1)
Analysis of the respondents' opinions about pink product

Phrase number	Mean	Standard Deviation	relative importance	degree of agreement
1	4.14	0.775	2	high
2	4.18	0.823	1	high
3	3.74	0.978	6	high
4	3.96	0.834	3	high
5	3.82	0.853	5	high

6	3.86	0.838	4	high
Total mean and standard deviation	3.95	0.570		high

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

The statistical analysis results in the above table indicate that the total mean of women sample responses was (3.95) with a standard deviation of (0.570), which is less than one and indicates low dispersion in women study sample responses, they also indicate a high degree of agreement for all pink product phrases which means that this element has an impact on women's purchasing decisions.

Table (2)
Analysis of the respondents' opinions about pink price

Phrase number	Mean	Standard Deviation	relative importance	degree of agreement
7	3.84	1.102	2	high
8	3.78	1.169	3	high
9	3.91	1.032	1	high
10	3.09	1.212	4	high
Total mean and standard deviation	3.66	0.813		high

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

The statistical analysis results in the above table indicate that the total mean of women sample responses was (3.66) with a standard deviation of (0.813), which is less than one and indicates low dispersion in women study sample responses, they also indicate a high degree of agreement for all pink price phrases, which means that this element has an impact on women's purchasing decisions.

Table (3)
Analysis of the respondents' opinions about pink promotion

Phrase number	Mean	Standard Deviation	relative importance	degree of agreement
11	3.21	1.243	5	high
12	3.25	1.134	4	high
13	3.80	1,130	1	high
14	3.76	1.147	2	high
15	3.67	1.256	3	high
Total mean and standard deviation	3.54	0.719		

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

The statistical analysis results in the above table indicate that the total mean of women sample responses was (3.54) with a standard deviation of (0.719), which is less than one and indicates low dispersion in women study sample responses, they also indicate a high degree of agreement for all pink promotion phrases which means that this element has an impact on women's purchasing decisions.

Table (4)
Analysis of the respondents' opinions about pink distribution

Phrase number	Mean	Standard Deviation	degree of agreement	degree of agreement
16	3.68	1.088	1	high
17	3.08	1.209	3	high
18	3.01	1.196	4	high
19	3.63	0.998	2	high
20	2.31	1.154	5	high
Total mean and standard deviation	3.14	0.655		high

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

The statistical analysis results in the above table indicate that the total mean of women sample responses was (3.14) with a standard deviation of (0.655), which is less than one and indicates low dispersion in women study sample responses, they also indicate a high degree of agreement for all pink distribution phrases which means that this element has an impact on women's purchasing decisions.

Table (5)
Analysis of the respondents' opinions about woman's purchasing decision

Phrase number	Mean	Standard Deviation	relative importance	degree of agreement
21	3.68	1.12245	8	high
22	4.31	.65094	1	high
23	3.79	.96199	7	high
24	3.89	.86749	5	high
25	3.85	1.01958	6	high
26	4.08	.94645	3	high
27	4.22	.85222	2	high
28	4.01	.76856	4	high
Total mean and standard deviation	3.98	.568		high

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

The statistical analysis results in the above table indicate that the total mean of women sample responses was (3.98) with a standard deviation of (0.568), which is less than one, and indicates low dispersion in women study sample responses, they also indicate a high degree of agreement for all woman's purchasing decision phrases, which means that pink marketing mix elements have an impact on women's purchasing

11.2 Hypotheses Testing

11.2.1 The main hypothesis

11.2.1 The main hypothesis

Ho: There isn't any statistical significant impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions.

Ha: There is a statistically significant impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the table below:

Table (6)
Multiple Regression Analysis of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions

Sig	t	Standardized Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	Model 1	
		Beta	Std. Error	B	
.000	4.374	.602	.518	2.268	(Constant)
.000	6.653	.586	.111	.737	pink product
.007	6.381	.247	.079	.503	pink price
.003	2.254	.227	.107	.240	pink
.005	2.874		.101	.289	promotion
					pink
					distribution

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

It's clear from the data in the above table that all of the pink marketing mix elements had an impact on women's purchasing decisions: The first, is the pink product, with (.602) as a value of the independent variable coefficient (Beta), and).000(as a statistical significance, followed by pink promotion with (.247) as a value of the

independent variable coefficient (Beta), and .003) as a statistical significance, followed by pink distribution with (.227) as a value of the independent variable coefficient Beta, and (.005) as a statistical significance, followed by pink price with (.586) as a value of the independent variable coefficient Beta, and (.007) as a statistical significance, which means rejecting the null hypothesis H_0 , which states that there isn't any statistically significant impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions, and accept alternative hypothesis H_a .

11.2.2 The First Sub-Hypothesis

H_{01} : There isn't any statistically significant impact of the pink product on women's purchasing decisions.

H_{a1} : There is a statistical significant impact of the pink product on women's purchasing decisions.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the table below:

Table 7

Multiple Regression Analysis of pink product on women's purchasing decisions

Sig	t	Standardized Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	Model 2	
		Beta	Std. Error	B	
.000	6.653	.602	.111	.737	pink product

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

clear from the data in the above table that pink product had an impact on women's purchasing decisions, with (.602) as a value of the independent variable coefficient (Beta), and .000(as a statistical significance, which means rejecting the null hypothesis H_{01} , which states that there isn't any statistical significant impact of the pink product on women's purchasing decisions, and accept alternative hypothesis H_{a1} .

11.2.3 The Second Sub-Hypothesis

H_{02} : There isn't any statistical significant impact of pink price on women's purchasing decisions.

H_{a2} : There is a statistical significant impact of pink price on women's purchasing decisions.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the table below:

Table 8

Multiple Regression Analysis of pink price on women's purchasing decisions

Sig	t	Standardized Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	Model 3	
		Beta	Std. Error	B	
.007	6.381	.586	.079	.503	pink price

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

It's clear from the data in the above table that pink price had an impact on women's purchasing decisions, with (.586) as a value of the independent variable coefficient (Beta), and .007(as a statistical significance, which means rejecting the null hypothesis H_{02} , which states that there isn't any statistical significant impact of pink price on women's purchasing decisions, and accept alternative hypothesis H_{a2} .

11.2.4 The Third Sub-Hypothesis

H_{03} : There isn't any statistical significant impact of pink promotion on women's purchasing decisions.

H_{a3} : There is a statistical significant impact of pink promotion on women's purchasing decisions.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the table below:

Table 9

Multiple Regression Analysis of pink promotion on women's purchasing decisions

Sig	t	Standardized Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	Model 4	
		Beta	Std. Error	B	
.003	2.254	.247	.107	.240	pink promotion

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

It's clear from the data in the above table that pink promotion had an impact on women's purchasing decisions, with (.247) as a value of the independent variable coefficient (Beta), and .003(as a statistical significance, which means rejecting the null hypothesis Ho3, which states that there isn't any statistical significant impact of pink promotion on women's purchasing decisions, and accept alternative hypothesis Ha3.

11.2.5 The Fourth Sub-Hypothesis

Ho4: There isn't any statistical significant impact of pink distribution on women's purchasing decisions.

Ha4: There is a statistical significant impact of pink distribution on women's purchasing decisions.

Multiple regression analysis has been used to test this hypothesis; the results are shown in the table below:

Table 10
Multiple Regression Analysis of pink distribution on women's purchasing decisions

Sig	t	Standardized Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	Model 5	
		Beta	Std. Error	B	
.005	2.874	.227	.101	.289	pink distribution

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the results of SPSS20

It's clear from the data in the above table that pink distribution had an impact on women's purchasing decisions, with (.227) as a value of the independent variable coefficient (Beta), and .005(as a statistical significance, which means rejecting the null hypothesis Ho4, which states that there isn't any statistical significant impact of pink distribution on women's purchasing decisions, and accept alternative hypothesis Ha4.

12. Results, Conclusions and Marketing Implications, and Recommendations

12.1 Results

1. Both the statistical analysis results (Table1), and the first sub-hypothesis test results (Table7) indicated that there is an impact of the pink product element on women's purchasing decisions.
2. Both the statistical analysis results (Table2) and the second sub-hypothesis test results (Table8) indicated that there is an impact of the pink price element on women's purchasing decisions.
3. Both the statistical analysis results (Table3), and the third sub- hypothesis test results (Table9) indicated that there is an impact of pink promotion elements on women's purchasing decisions.
4. Both the statistical analysis results (Table4), and the fourth sub-hypothesis test results (Table10) indicated that there is an impact of the pink distribution element on women's purchasing decisions.
5. Both the statistical analysis results (Table5), and the main hypothesis test results (Table 6) indicated that there is an impact of pink marketing mix elements on women's purchasing decisions.

12.2 Conclusions and Marketing Implications

1. Pink marketing is all the marketing efforts implemented to apply a suitable women's pink marketing mix, to satisfy their needs and desires through it. Women also pay much attention to details while acquiring goods and services, so this aspect must be taken into account in the marketing process, and because women are characterized by hesitation, dealers must be patient while dealing with them.
2. Pink marketing is of great importance to organizations that use it because it has an impact on women's purchasing decisions.
3. Pink marketing is not limited to women as customers only, but also to women as marketers, when they influence customer's purchasing decisions, whether they are men or women.
4. For a woman, the purchasing process is essential in her life, as she considers it a means to satisfy her needs and desires, as well as a means of entertainment and fun.
5. Women pay much attention to details while acquiring goods and services, so this aspect must be taken into account in the marketing process, and because women are characterized by hesitation, dealers must be patient while dealing with them.
6. Organizations can influence women's purchasing decisions by using various price methods, such as discounts, free samples, and other methods.
7. Pink marketing is not limited to the use of pink color in products, but also includes every product directed to women that can carry any other color, red, yellow, orange, etc.
8. For a woman, the purchasing process is linked to pink marketing mix elements used to present products to her.

9. Establishing institutions supporting pink marketing, such as using pink marketing in the field of health services, and this can be applied by institutions and associations concerned with protecting women from cancer, especially breast cancer.

12.3 Recommendations

1. More attention must be paid to the pink marketing concept because it was found that most women are not aware of this concept.
2. Study of women's markets enables organizations to build marketing mix strategies that are consistent with women's needs and desires, as well as to determine the marketing strategy to be followed in case of changes that may occur in markets.
3. It is possible to influence women's purchasing decisions by designing products that are compatible with their personality and characterized by attractiveness in both their colors and shapes.
4. Interior design of stores, method of displaying products, and lighting effect woman's psyche and are factors that attract women.
5. Attempting to bridge the gap that occurred when a woman can't find what she's looking for, by providing products that meet her needs and desires.
6. Trying to understand a woman's personality when dealing with her during the selling phase, because women are different in their personality.
7. Paying more attention to the distribution side, in terms of providing products continuously without discontinuation, because sometimes a woman purchases a product and after a while when she comes back to purchase it, she does not find it in the market.
8. Paying more attention to the distribution side, in terms of providing products continuously without discontinuation, because sometimes a woman purchases a product and after a while when she comes back to purchase it, she does not find it in the market.

Study prospects

During the completion of this research, some related topics came to our attention that may be addressed by researchers in the future, as follows:

- The role of word of mouth in activating pink marketing.
- Electronic pink marketing and its impact on consumer behavior.
- The effect of marketing strategies on studying women's behavior.
- The role of pink marketing in achieving differentiation strategy.

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